

Social Anxiety, Social Support And Self Esteem In Female Victims of Catcalling

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Abstract

Self-esteem is very important for everyone, especially women. Sexual harassment such as catcalling will make women feel their self-esteem is lowered and humiliated. This study aims to determine the effect of social support and social anxiety on self-esteem in female victims of catcalling. The participants in this study were 65 female victims of catcalling. Data collection was carried out using a questionnaire. The results of this study indicate that social anxiety and social support together have an influence on self-esteem by 18.4%, but when viewed partially only social anxiety has an influence on self-esteem while social support is not found to have an influence on self-esteem in women victims of catcalling.

Keywords: *social support, social anxiety, self-esteem, women, catcalling*

INTRODUCTION

Oxford Dictionaries defines catcalling as comments of a sexual nature made by a man to a passing woman. Catcalling is a form of sexual harassment, or unwanted verbal or nonverbal sexual attention, also aptly described as stranger harassment because the victim and perpetrator do not know each other (Fairchild and Rudman 2008). Catcalling usually occurs in public places, such as in public transportation, public roads, city parks, and others. However, not many women realize the treatment as harassment. They think catcalling is a normal thing for men to do. For women, it is better for them to avoid catcalling by changing the road route, mode of transportation, or the way they dress. These efforts are reasonable considering that women's bodies are always attached to the judgment of society. If a woman becomes a victim of harassment, most people tend to blame the victim by

questioning how she dresses, her behavior, when and where the harassment occurred (Andriasanti, 2017).

Women who have experienced catcalling feel that their self-esteem is lowered and humiliated. Self-esteem is very important for women. Self-esteem is a personal assessment of worthiness expressed in the attitudes that individuals hold about themselves (Mongelluzzo, 2012). It is very important for individuals to maintain their self-esteem as well as social relationships, thus maintaining a sense of social support. High self-esteem is important for better physical and psychological health for which social support from both family and peers is required. (Tahir, Inam & Raana, 2015). According to House, Umberson and Landis (1988) social support can be defined as the quality of support from social relationships as perceived by a person. It can be explained as the degree to which a person believes that support from social relationships is available to him, this support can be in any form including emotional support, information or tangible support and may be available from significant others, family members and peers.

People who have better levels of support in their social relationships are healthier physically and psychologically compared to individuals with relatively lower support (Barrera, 1986). Demaray, Malecki, Davidson, Hodgson and Rebus (2005) found an association between low social support and general psychological distress and other emotional problems. For this reason, there needs to be social support from several groups for this case including the government, at least there are several steps that leaders in a region can take later. By encouraging the legislature at the regional level to parse and detail the Criminal Code related to sexual harassment so that it becomes a woman-friendly regional regulation. Then they must educate and prepare law enforcement officers who are gender-sensitive and care about women's issues. They must also introduce and instill an understanding of gender equality from an early age through education. This aims to create future generations who respect each other and do not demean others for sexual reasons (Andriasanti, 2017).

This form of social support can make women victims of catcalling feel valued and protected. If women victims of catcalling receive good social support

from their environment, their social anxiety can decrease so that they can respect themselves and assess themselves well, but if social support from their environment is low, it can increase the social anxiety of women victims of catcalling and cause them to judge themselves badly and be humiliated.

The results of research from Bhat (2017) on the relationship between social support and self-esteem in students in India show that social support is directly related to self-esteem. The results show that higher levels of social support indicate better self-esteem among people. People who receive good social support from various sources have a better view of their own self-esteem. Furthermore, research from Kumar, Lal and Bhuchar (2014) shows that there is a positive relationship between social support and self-esteem besides according to Nolen (1999) which was found through research that individuals with high self-esteem are likely to have more social support.

In addition to social support, another factor that can affect individual self-esteem is social anxiety. Social anxiety is a feeling of discomfort in the presence of others that is always accompanied by feelings of shame characterized by awkwardness or stiffness, inhibition and a tendency to avoid social interactions (Dayakisni & Hudaniah, 2009). It is not only men in Indonesia who consider catcalling to be commonplace, but also almost all over the world. Victims of catcalling are not only women in revealing clothing but can happen to any woman in any clothing and any race (Alfian, 2017). In the end, this makes women tend to become uncomfortable and worried when going out alone, feeling shy, insecure and other things that lead to social anxiety levels. One Cornell University study in 2014 found that 50% of women in more than 22 countries had reported being groped or fondled due to street harassment (Davidson, et al, 2013). Not only are words of praise but can be perceived as demeaning and objectifying comments that have a negative impact on women's psychological well-being. The women viewed themselves as part of the perpetrators' bodies, body parts and sexual functions. The women feel more conscious and embarrassed about their bodies and their body parts which leads to self-objectification in women because when they experience this women feel anxious about how their bodies are evaluated by strangers.

Research conducted by Liaqat and Akram (2014) regarding the relationship between self-esteem and social anxiety in people who experience physical disabilities, the results showed that the level of self-esteem has a major influence on the level of social anxiety in people who have physical disabilities. If the level of self-esteem is low then social anxiety will be high. The results also show that physically disabled women have lower levels of self-esteem and higher levels of social anxiety compared to men who have physical disabilities. Furthermore, research from Fatima, Niazi and Ghayas (2017) shows that there is a negative relationship between self-esteem and social anxiety. In addition, according to Lasgaard and Elklit (2009) people with low self-esteem try to be socially isolated and experience decreased connections.

RESEARCH METHODS

In accordance with the research objectives, namely examining the influence of social anxiety and social support on self-esteem, this study uses a quantitative approach. The population in this study were women who were victims or had experienced catcalling. With a sample of 65 respondents. The scale contains measuring instruments for the research variables, plus other necessary information such as name (initials), age, status, how often the respondent experiences catcalling, what the respondent does when responding to the perpetrator of catcalling and who the respondent is with when catcalling occurs. Respondents indicated whether these conditions were consistent with their circumstances at the time of the incident.

Social anxiety was measured based on scores on a scale adapted from Tirsae (2016) which was then modified by the researcher. The scale refers to aspects of social anxiety from La Greca and Lopez (2005), namely fear of being negatively evaluated, social avoidance and distress in new situations, and social avoidance and distress experienced in general with new people. One example of an item in this scale is “When I am in public, I feel that people can do bad things to me”. The answer options range from 1-4 ranging from very appropriate to very inappropriate, this scale totals 21 items with a reliability of 0.850.

Social support is measured based on scores on a scale adapted from Hastari (2018) which refers to the theory and scale of Zimet, et al (1988). The scale is used to measure the level of social support a person receives, if the score obtained is higher, the higher the level of social support received and vice versa, if the score obtained is lower, the lower the level of social support received. One example of an item in this scale is “I can tell my problems to my family”. The answer options range from 1-4 ranging from very appropriate to very inappropriate, this scale totals 12 items with a reliability of 0.759.

Self-esteem is measured based on scores on a scale adapted from Gunawan (2018) which was then modified by the researcher. The scale refers to Coopersmith's (1967) theory or known as CSEI (Coopersmith Self Esteem Inventory). CSEI measures the level of self-esteem based on aspects of self-esteem from Coopersmith, namely power, virtue, significance and competence. One example of an item in this scale is “I can understand myself”. The answer options range from 1-4 ranging from very appropriate to very inappropriate, this scale totals 20 items with a reliability of 0.808.

Testing the discrimination power of an item is done by calculating the correlation coefficient between the distribution of item scores and the distribution of scale scores itself which will produce an aitem-total correlation coefficient. In this study, to test the discrimination power of researchers using Item Total Correlation analysis with the help of the IBM SPSS for windows program. Reliability testing in this study was carried out internal consistency testing. To test the reliability in this study, researchers used Cronbach's Alpha analysis with the help of the IBM SPSS for windows program. In accordance with the research objectives, namely the effect of social anxiety and social support on self-esteem. In this study, the analysis carried out is to examine the effect of social anxiety variables (X1) on self-esteem (Y); social support variables (X2) on self-esteem (Y), and social anxiety variables (X1), social support (X2) on self-esteem (Y), so the technique used to test the hypothesis is multiple regression analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis testing is done using multiple regression. The results show a significance of 0.002 which indicates that the results are significant and the variables of social anxiety and social support can be used to predict self-esteem.

Table 1 is the result of the analysis that the significance of multiple regression between social anxiety and support together in this study is 0.002 ($p < 0.05$), this means that there is a significant influence between social anxiety and social support together on self-esteem in female victims of catcalling. The R square value found is 0.184. This means that social anxiety and social support in this study have an influence of 18.4% on self-esteem in female victims of catcalling, while 81.6% is another factor outside the study.

Table 2 is the result of the coefficient analysis of social anxiety and social support on self-esteem. Social anxiety has a greater influence on self-esteem than social support. The results show the significance of social anxiety of 0.001 ($p < 0.05$) which means there is an influence of social anxiety on self-esteem in women victims of catcalling, while the significance of social support is 0.235 ($p < 0.05$) which means there is no influence between social support on self-esteem in women victims of catcalling. The influence of social anxiety variables on self-esteem is 42.2% while 57.8% is another factor outside the study, then the influence of social support variables on self-esteem is 13.8% while 86.2% is another factor outside the study.

Table 1. Regression Test Results of Social Anxiety and Social Support on Self Esteem

F	Sig	R Square
7,010	0,002	0,184

Table 2. Results of the Overall Coefficient of Social Anxiety and Social Support on Self Esteem

Model	B	Coefficients		T	Sig
		Unstandardized	Standardized		
		Coefficients	Coefficients		
		Std. Error	Beta		

(Constant)	21,772	4.594		4.739	.000
Social Anxiety	.361	.099	.422	3.655	.001
Social Support	.089	.074	.138	1.199	.235

Based on the results of testing the research hypothesis, it is obtained that the hypothesis proposed in this study, namely there is an influence of social anxiety on self-esteem in female victims of catcalling; accepted, there is an influence of social support on self-esteem in female victims of catcalling; rejected, but the hypothesis there is an influence of social anxiety and social support on self-esteem in female victims of catcalling is accepted. The results of the analysis in this study indicate that one of the two minor hypotheses is accepted and the major hypothesis in this study is accepted. This indicates that social anxiety and social support together have an influence on self-esteem in female victims of catcalling.

In this research, the social anxiety variable has the greatest influence on self-esteem. Social anxiety is a feeling of discomfort with the presence of other people which is always accompanied by feelings of shame characterized by awkwardness or stiffness, inhibition and a tendency to avoid social interaction (Dayakisni & Hudaniah, 2009). According to the results of research from Liaqat and Akram (2014), the results show that the lower the level of self-esteem, the higher the social anxiety and if the level of self-esteem is high, the social anxiety will be low. The results of the study were also supported by Untari, Bahri and Fajriani (2017) in their research on 1463 respondents, and research from Tirsae (2016) with 143 respondents who stated that there was a significant influence between social anxiety and self-esteem. Oort, et al (2011) say that the factors that cause social anxiety are due to traumatic experiences such as persecution, intimidation and threats from peers. In relation to the results of the study which show that there is an influence of social anxiety on self-esteem in female victims of catcalling, this shows that women will feel anxious about the social environment when they experience verbal harassment that occurs in public places such as catcalling.

In addition to the social support variable, it was found that there was no influence on self-esteem in women victims of catcalling, this could be due to sample factors that did not represent the existing population, namely the sample obtained

in this study of 65 respondents, besides that women who experienced catcalling had a good level of self-esteem regardless of the social support received. These results are in accordance with the results of research from Indrastiti and Prihastuti (2017) in their research on 22 respondents showed the results that there was no effect of social support on self-esteem, this could be due to the small number of respondents and the situations and conditions experienced by respondents when filling out the questionnaire. The process of developing self-esteem is highly dependent on acceptance, recognition, attention and also appreciation obtained from people around (Yadav & Iqbal, 2009). There are factors that can affect self-esteem besides social support including experience, parenting, environment, socioeconomics, and competence. The results of research from Naeem, et al (2014) show that there is no relationship between social support and self-esteem which indicates that people have self-esteem without the influence of social support, besides research from Herdiyanto and Surjaningrum (2014) also get similar results that there is no significant relationship between social support and self-esteem.

Based on the data of this study, social anxiety and social support together affect self-esteem in female victims of catcalling by 18.4%, so there may be other factors that have more influence on self-esteem that cannot be seen by researchers.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Summary

Based on the test results, it is found that social anxiety and social support together contribute to self-esteem in female victims of catcalling. In addition, only social anxiety can affect self-esteem in female victims of catcalling. The contribution of social anxiety is greater than social support to self-esteem while social support has no influence on self-esteem in female victims of catcalling.

Advice

Suggestions for future researchers who want to examine the influence of social anxiety variables and social support on self-esteem to pay attention to other

variables that have not been measured in research that can affect the self-esteem variables of women victims of catcalling. In addition, future researchers can take a larger number of respondents and can look for other variables that can affect self-esteem.

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